

Simultaneous measurements of metals and PAHs using diffusive gradients in thin films (DGT) with an environmentally friendly binding layer

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The Diffusive Gradients in Thin Films (DGT) technique is an in situ and preconcentration method which has been widely developed to measure either inorganic or organic contaminants using different resin layers in aquatic environment. However, it was never considered to use a single resin, containing multiple functional groups, for simultaneous determination of inorganic and organic compounds by a universal passive sampler. A new DGT sampler using an environmentally friendly Capterall Mersorb (CM) binding layer for simultaneous measurements of ten trace metals (Cd, Zn, Cr, Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Pb, Ag, Hg) and three Platinum group elements (PGEs) (Pd, Pt, Rh) was established in this study using DGT with. The binding kinetics of each element in a mixed solution indicated a rapid uptake by the CM resin gels. The capacities of CM gel for Cd, Zn and Cu were 381, 320 and 202 $\mu\text{g disc}^{-1}$ respectively, which were comparable to chelex-100 resin gel, which is commonly used for trace metal sampling in DGT. Moreover, CM-DGT was combined with a chemically activated luciferase gene expression bioassay (CALUX) to measure polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in aquatic systems. CALUX bioassay measures the sum of biological and toxicological effects of PAHs, instead of individual compound concentration. Benzo[a]pyrene (BaP) as the model of PAHs, has been efficiently uptaken by CM gel. The combination of DGT and CALUX bioassay shows a great potential to measure the group of PAHs compounds in situ and at very low concentration levels. Therefore, this novel DGT sampler provides a possibility to simultaneously determine inorganic and organic contaminants for the first time in aquatic systems.

Figure 1. Uptake percentage (%) of metals by CM resin in $500 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ solutions containing 0.05 M NaCl (A). Accumulated mass (μg) of Zn (B), Cu (C) and Cd (D) on CM resin gel discs by deployment for 16 h in solutions containing mixed elements of Zn, Cu and Cd in a concentration range of 5–600 μg .

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